

EFFECT OF INTER-PLY SLIDING ON THE APPEARANCE OF DEFECTS FOR MULTI-LAYERED COMPOSITE SHAPING

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Introduction

The transport sector is one of the fastest growing consumer of energy and producer of greenhouse gases in the world. Consequently, transportation means with a low energy consumption, and thus global warming, are more and more demanding as being a major concern again the protection of the environment and hence respect a durable development. This aim can be achieved by reducing the mass of the transportation means and this by replacing metallic materials by composites ones on structural parts subjected to severe mechanical solicitations and this with equal mechanical performances. Indeed, composite materials are able to propose credible answers to the optimization of the thick structural parts with significant size through their good ratio strength/weight and especially their anisotropy which can be adapted to the mechanical solicitation of the structure.

To manufacture the composites pieces, LCM processes are the more interesting ones because they offer the best compromise in terms of repeatability, production rates and low final cost. The first step of the processes consists in draping a dry preform before injection of the liquid resin. This stage is a delicate phase and the mechanisms taking place are complex and different than the ones occurring during the stamping of metallic sheets. These mechanisms are far from being fully understood [1] which hampers the mastery of the manufacturing process and development of composite materials. In addition, the increasing use of materials with low environmental effect (biomaterials ...) and complex weaving architectures (interlock, 3D fabrics), makes it more difficult.

Among the strategies useable to investigate a priori the formability of a given fabric on a given shape,

finite element simulation and experimental demonstrators can be considered. The complementarity between these two methods will enable to understand and model accurately the performing step and will hopefully permit to decrease the cost and time needed for the tools and fabrics development.

Many methods have been proposed recently to achieve representative sheet forming simulations of dry fabric, with different approaches [2-4]. These studies need several key entries such as the dry fabric mechanical properties and the fabric/tool friction coefficient, which have been widely studied [5-8]. The obtained results must be validated with experimental data of woven reinforcement forming using experimental approaches [9-12].

When dealing with the multilayer forming of thick composite parts, a significant relative sliding of the layers occurs [13]. This sliding generates inter-ply friction that is of significant when dealing with composite forming. In fact, several numerical studies, some of which were correlated with experimental results, have highlighted this effect both in dry fabric forming that during forming of pre-consolidated laminated composites [14-17]. These studies showed that the final preform depends heavily on the inter-ply friction. However, these studies were carried out on simple preforms geometris (like dome) on which little or no faults occur.

Moreover, studies conducted on dry reinforcements used nonwoven reinforcement (NCF) [13, 17]. The effect of the inter-ply friction of this kind of fabric will be less severe than the woven fabrics because the phenomena that occur during friction of woven, such as shocks of overhanging yarns, are not present [18, 19]. So forming woven fabric reinforcement can leads to the defects apparition or their amplification.

Far as we know, there is no study done on complex shapes made with woven dry reinforcements. These non-developable shapes lead to higher shear angles (up to 60°) and various defaults [10, 20]. So the knowledge and understanding of the effect of friction on the behaviour of the preform is necessary for mastering processes.

The aim of this study is then to investigate experimentally the effect of fabric/fabric friction behavior on defects apparition when dealing with multilayered highly double curved shaping of composite dry fabric. For this purpose, forming tests using an interlock fabric are carried out. The results obtained on single layers and multilayers forming are compared focusing on defects quantification and measured shear angles.

Material and method

Tested Fabric:

The tests presented in this paper are carried out on a commercial composite woven reinforcement used in aeronautic field. It is a powdered interlock fabric, denoted Hexcel G1151[®], with an areal weight of 630 g/m² and is comprised of T300JB 6K yarns (Figure 1). The nominal construction is 7.5 yarns/cm for warp and 7.4 yarns/cm for weft. The G1151[®] unit cell consists of 6 warp yarns and 15 weft yarns, with the weft yarns being distributed on three levels. In situ average yarn width is about 2mm for warp and 3mm for weft. The mechanical behaviors of this fabric and its formability have been widely studied.

Figure 1: Woven carbon reinforcement (G1151[®]).

Forming device:

Experimental device developed in our lab in collaboration with EADS Company was used to

carry the preforming tests (Figure 2) [9]. It is composed of three parts. The first part consists in a pair punch/open-die that can be easily changed and adapted. The punch is moved using an electric jack in order to control easily and accurately the punch position and speed. Sensors enable to track: the position, speed and load exerted by the punch.

The die is chosen open to carry optical measurement on the fabric during stamping using the second part of the device composed by a stereo vision system. This system is composed by two commercial charge coupled device (CCD) cameras that can be positioned in function of the specific zone of the fabric that has to be analyzed. They are connected to a computer and permit to record continuously images of the samples during the shaping process. The maximum image resolution of these cameras is 1380×1024 pixels with a 8-bit digitization for grey levels (28=256 grey levels). The maximal acquisition frequency is one image per second. Images are recorded, digitized and stored in a computer as digital images. They can be post-processed, using software based on digital Image Correlation (DIC) or marker tracking techniques, in order to calculate the displacement fields and thus the strain fields if needed.

Figure 2: Experimental device for fabric shaping

The third part of the device is constituted by a blank holder system: two mechanisms have been designed. The first one is a classical multi-part blank holder. It is composed of maximum 9 independent blank holders actuated by maximum 9 pneumatic jacks that enable to impose and sensor independently a variable pressure on each of them. Here again the system has been designed so that the contact zones

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of the blank holders can be easily manufactured and changed to investigate the influence of their geometry on the process. The second disposal is designed to replace the blank holders by a fixed tension on the yarns extremities. This disposal is dedicated to investigate the real impact of the pressure and friction forces applied by the blank holders. It enables an easier comparison with finite element simulation since the complex phenomenon of pressure and friction between the yarns and the blank holders does not need to be modeled in this case.

Tests conditions:

There is a complex relationship between the fabric mechanical properties, the forming process parameters (blank holder pressure distribution) and the part shape. Since our study concerns the effect of the interplay sliding on the defects appearance, test conditions and adequate shape allowing defects appearance must be chosen.

The first important point is the choice of a highly double curved shape that can generate a wide range of defects with maximum amplitudes. In fact, if experimental data on simple shapes such as hemisphere can be found here and there, this shape does not promote the appearance of defects. For this purpose, a prismatic punch with a triple point, that is highly non-expandable with small curvature radii, used previously for forming a case corner has been chosen for this study (Figure 3). The dimension of the punch and the die can be found in [20].

Figure 3: Prismatic shape used for this study.

The second point concerns the forming process parameters which must be chosen according to the fabric behaviors. To form complex shapes such as the one concerned in this study, the fabric may accommodate large in-plane shear deformation. It was shown that the G1151® fabric is particularly adapted to this deformation mode, with a high value of the locking angle ($\sim 55\text{--}60^\circ$) [5, 7].

Figure 4: Initial positioning of the fabric for the two configurations of multilayer forming

When the shear reaches the “locking angle” values, the shear stiffness becomes too high and the fabric starts wrinkling. A wrinkle is an out of plane phenomenon appearing when less energy is needed for an out of plane deformation than for an in-plane deformation. It is one of the most well known forming defects that has to be avoided because it results in a significant decrease of the mechanical properties of the final composite part. However, the only notion of locking angle is not sufficient to anticipate the presence of wrinkles. Indeed, the wrinkling phenomena: position, shape, number..., is strongly related to the bending stiffness of the layer but also to the tensile loading on the fabric [21]. Coupling between shear and tension has been

noticed in different papers through an increase of the locking angle observed by different teams during picture frame tests with pretension [5, 22]. This means that it is possible to obtain high shear deformation where the shear angle is higher than the locking angle if tension is applied to the fabric. So, a rise of the blank-holder pressure has the tendency to delay the appearing of wrinkles [20].

Furthermore, increasing the applied tension on yarns leads to significant residual stresses in the fabric. The consistency of reinforcement may then be undermined resulting in other defects such as broken yarns and/or "weave pattern heterogeneity" phenomenon [20]. These defects are more severe on the used shape; this is why the drawing with a high blank holder pressure was chosen for this study to ensure maximum defects on the final parts.

Based on the above analyze, tests were carried out with one layer and then with several layers of dry fabric with the same test conditions. Two configurations were realized. In the first one, the fabric has been initially positioned with the weft and warp network parallel to the edges of the punches faces (see Figure 4. a). This configuration have been tested with one layer and then with two layers. For the second configuration, interlock fabric were placed as illustrated in Figure 4. b when shaping two plies. For the second configuration, two plies of the fabric were placed as illustrated in Figure 4.b before shaping tests. To compare this test results with a single-ply ones, a forming test was performed with a single fold oriented at 45° like the lower fold on the Figure 4.b.

Eight blank holders were used around the preform in order to apply tension on the yarns through the fabric/metal friction. A blank holder pressure of 4bars is applied by the pneumatic jacks that correspond to an applied force of 9.22N/yarn. After positioning the fabric, the punch moved with a speed of 30 mm/ min and images were recorded using the CCD cameras.

After forming tests, defects and shear angles were quantified in the useful shape areas for each test then quantitative and qualitative comparisons were made between the different configurations.

Results and discussion

Configuration 1

The forming tests according to the configuration 1 (see Figure 4. a) give a good shapes

quality at the macroscopic level. An outside view of the preforms, realized with one and two layers, shows that the agreement with the punch shape at the end of the forming is pretty good (Figure 5).

Figure 5: View of the prismatic shape for two layers forming according to configuration 1.

Wrinkles appear as it was foreseen but not in the useful part. These wrinkles have no consequence on the composite parts quality since the non-useful zones will be cut after the process. These results confirm first the influence of the tension in yarns, due to the blank-holder pressure, on the presence of wrinkle.

Another type of defect denoted "out of plane buckles" appears on faces and edges of the prismatic preforms (Figure 6). The "out of plane buckles" could be assimilated to the out of plane buckling of yarns that can be compared to the wrinkling phenomenon but this one takes place at the scale of the fabric, whereas buckling takes place at the scale of yarns [20]. Locally these buckles constitute a consequent over thickness that leads to local heterogeneity of the fabric. For the prismatic shapes realised according to configuration 1, they are localized on the triangular faces, at the middle of the face but also on the diagonal edges, separating the triangular to the rectangular faces. They are localized on zones of about 15 to 35 mm width.

Location and magnitudes of the wrinkles and buckles defects are almost the same for single-ply and two layers prismatic shapes realized according to the configuration1.

Figure 6 shows the measured shear angles on the frontal face of the two plies shape where the fabric is the most stressed. The angles vary between 46° and 50° when the measured angles for the single-ply

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shape are about $49^{\circ \pm 1}$. They shear angles remain relatively the same between the single ply and the two plies final shapes. In addition, the highest shear angles were achieved in the base corners (up to 55°) but without creating wrinkles, which still shows once again the effect of blank holder pressure on delaying of wrinkles appearance (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Shear angles and defects on the frontal face of the prismatic shape of two layers forming according to configuration 1.

It can be concluded that the friction has no significant effect on the behavior of the preform at the outer faces and this despite the inter-ply sliding that occurs when the two plies forming is carried out. Indeed, the zone appearance of defects and their magnitude as well as the shear angles of the fabric remains relatively unchanged for the two final shapes. This is probably due to the low relative observed sliding between the plies.

This observation is not the same when we interested to defects that occur on the inner faces of the final shapes. In fact, when we look at the inner faces of the preform, we observe additional defects that do not appear on the outer faces and a difference between the single-layer and multilayer.

The “out of plane buckles” appear at the same areas and with the same magnitude on the inner and outer faces of the single-ply and two-ply shapes (Figure 7 detail a).

However, additional defects such as wrinkles, broken fibres and buckles appear on areas of the inner faces whereas they were not observed on the outer surfaces (Figure 7 detail d). Indeed, fibre breakage was observed on the prismatic shape's triple points but with a largest range in the case of multilayer shape. This fibre damage is not due to

tension introduced by the blank holder's pressure because it is lower than the yarns maximum strength [20]. It is probably due to the severe stresses generated by the boundary conditions (small curvature radii of the triple point), the ply/ply friction behaviour and the pressure exerted by the upper layer on the lower one.

Detail a

detail b

Detail c

detail d

Figure 7: View of the inner faces of the two layers prismatic shape formed according to configuration 1

These conditions are also likely the cause of buckles associated to “weave pattern heterogeneity” that were observed on the base corners of the inner faces (Figure 7 detail b). These defects were only observed in the inner faces of the shape formed with two interlock layers. They were not expected because a high shear angles occur at these areas. The “weave pattern heterogeneity” is caused by a relative slip of the weft and warp yarns and leads to a very

low local yarn density [20]. This type of defect depends mainly on the complexity of the shape, the boundary condition as well as the cohesion of the fabric weaving.

Figure 8: Phenomena occur during fabric/fabric contact behavior: yarn/yarn friction and shock phenomenon caused by overhanging [19]

Figure 9: Evolution of tangential load during fabric/fabric friction test of G1151[®] reinforcement.

On the upper faces of the preform, wrinkles were observed for the multilayer shape (Figure 7 detail c). This defect should not appear on this area because the high blank holder's pressure. This defect is due to the effect of the ply/ply friction behavior that occurs due to the interplay sliding. Indeed, it has been shown that fabric/fabric contact behavior consists in the superposition of two phenomena (Figure 8) [19]. The first one is on the yarn/yarn sliding friction that occurs between the yarns oriented in direction of the movement. The second phenomenon is the shocks that take place between the transverse overhanging yarns of each ply, at each period of the unit cell. This second phenomenon generates a high reaction force that leads to increasing maximum friction values. Reaction force

due to this phenomenon increases leading to high maximum friction values (peaks of Figure 9). Shocks phenomenon that occurs will result in hampering the interplay relative sliding because of the high tangential forces generated value (peaks) with respect to the tension exerted on the yarns by the blank holder pressure. It follows that this obstacle will promote the appearance of wrinkles.

Configuration 2

The shapes realized according to configuration 2 showed more extensive defects. The external view of the single-layer shape shows wrinkles and “weave pattern heterogeneity on the external faces in addition to the out of plane buckles. The buckles positions are not the same comparatively to the single-layer shape obtained according to configuration 1. This is due to the relative position between the fabric and the punch. However other defect appeared only in this configuration. These defects were attributed to the effect of the relative orientation between the fabric major networks (warp and weft) and the punch. In fact, this shape was formed with a fabric relative orientation of 45° with respect to the configuration 1. We can then conclude that the fabric initial position with respect to the punch has an effect on the type and amount of defects when dealing with highly double curved shapes. The measured shear angles (maximum between 42-48° for this shape) remain relatively the same between the two configurations.

Figure 10: View of the monolayer (oriented at 45°) prismatic shape formed according to configuration 2.

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Figure 11: View of the two-ply ($45^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$) prismatic shape formed according to configuration 2

Figure 12 shows the external view and defects location of the two-layers shape formed according to configuration 2. Note that the external layer is oriented at 0° . All defaults observed on the previous preforms are present on the outer ply faces and have increased compared to all achieved shapes (Figure 12). The reached shear angles are about 53 to 62° on the frontal faces. The shape is not acceptable in this state and this necessarily affects the injection process, but also the expected characteristics of the final composite part. This increase in the defects number and their magnitudes is attributed to the coupled effects of the initial plies fabric orientation (especially inner one) according to the punch but also the ply/ply friction due to the interplay sliding. Moreover, this fact is confirmed especially when comparing the inner faces of the two shapes (with a single-ply and two plies) obtained according to configuration 2 (Figure 12). These faces are those of plies having the same orientation (45°) with respect to the prismatic punch. It was observed that the type and location of defects remain substantially the same (Figure 12). However, their magnitudes and their quantities were significantly higher in the case of the preform obtained with two plies fabric. Knowing that these plies are obtained under the same conditions (orientation, blank holder's pressure, etc. ...) except the ply/ply friction that occurs for multilayer shaping. This leads us to conclude that the shock phenomenon between yarns which dominates the fabric/fabric friction is the main cause of this defects increase.

- ▬ wrinkle + weave pattern heterogeneity
- ▬ wrinkles
- ▬ Out of plane buckles
- Fiber broken

Figure 12: Defects comparison of the inner faces (oriented at 45°) of the single-layer and two layers prismatic shapes formed according to configuration 2

However, a previous study showed that the fabric/fabric Coulomb friction coefficient is sensitive to the relative orientation of the two samples [19]. It also showed that the average coefficient, and therefore the maximum tangential forces due to shocks between transverse and longitudinal yarns of the two samples, is more important when G1151[®] interlock samples are positioned to $0^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ then to $0^{\circ}/45^{\circ}$ [19]. Therefore the friction phenomenon should have more effect on the defects appearance on the shapes realized according to configuration 1 where the plies are oriented in the same direction.

But we must also consider that when forming multilayer shape according to the configuration 1, there has been a relatively small relative displacement between the two plies. However, the relative movement between folds that occurred on the second preform is significantly larger which was promoted by the relative position between the yarns networks (weft and warp) and the punch.

Conclusion

These experimental work concerns the study of the effect of inter-ply sliding on the defects appearance for multilayered composite shaping. Forming tests were carried out on single-layer and multilayer shapes. Two configurations, using different relative position between the plies and the punch, were considered.

Comparisons showed that the shear angles on different areas of interest are almost identical between the multilayered shapes and single-ply ones. For defects, the locations of areas on which they appear are the generally same. However, the magnitude of each defect and the extent of the affected areas are more significant in the case of multilayered shapes. Additional defects, such as fiber breakage, were also observed in the same areas for this configuration.

The measures and observations carried out in this study highlight the effect of the ply/ply friction behavior, due to relative sliding between layers, on the defects and their appearance. This is due to the shocks phenomenon that takes place between the transverse overhanging yarns of each ply, at each period of the unit cell. This phenomenon hampers the interplay relative sliding and generates high tangential forces with respect to the tension exerted on the yarns by the blank holder pressure. It follows that this obstacle will promote the wrinkles appearance.

It has been shown that the relative position between the ply and the highly non-expandable punch is important and promotes the inter-ply sliding and then defects appearance and/or their amplification for multilayered composite shaping.

Nevertheless, an intensive work remains to do in order to understand and master the coupling phenomena and relationships between defects, fabric mechanical behaviours, forming process parameters and the part shape.

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